

Supporting Information

Si/Ag/C Nanohybrids with *in situ* Incorporation of Super-Small Silver Nanoparticles: Tiny Amount, Huge Impact

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Figure S1. I-V curves of the Si/Ag/C nanohybrids with the silver composition of 0 % (a), 2.591 % (b), 3.994 % (c), and 4.552 % (d) at different temperatures.